

Report of the Structure and Deformation at Plate Boundaries GeoPRISMS Synthesis Workshop

March 16 - 18, 2022. University of Hawai'i at Mānoa, Honolulu, HI

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Organizing Committee

Helen Janiszewski (University of Hawai'i at Mānoa, Lead Organizer)

Cailey Condit (University of Washington)

Hiroko Kitajima (Texas A&M University)

D. Sarah Stamps (Virginia Tech)

[Workshop Website](#)

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Motivation:

Attendees of the 2019 GeoPRISMS Synthesis and Integration Theoretical and Experimental Institute (TEI) identified that small, interdisciplinary, science-question-focused workshops are an essential element of the final phase of the GeoPRISMS program. Additional input was received at the 2019 AGU Mini-Workshops, culminating in discussion regarding a coordinated set of workshops focused on science topics that cross-cut Rift Initiation and Evolution (RIE) and Subduction Cycles and Deformation (SCD) focus sites. The importance of encouraging early career involvement in both the planning stages and in attendance at these workshops was also heavily emphasized. To meet these community needs, two workshops were held in 2022 - Structure and Deformation at Plate Boundaries at the University of Hawai'i at Mānoa (this workshop), and Magma and Volatiles at Montana State University.

The goals for the Plate Boundary Structure and Deformation Workshop were: (1) to showcase recent GeoPRISMS research that has advanced our understanding of plate boundary structure and deformation with particular emphasis at both RIE and SCD focus sites; (2) to facilitate the formation of new, interdisciplinary collaborations, particularly for early career scientists and motivate future research collaborations; (3) to promote best practices for the archiving of data and educational materials; and (4) to produce outreach materials in the form of short videos to highlight GeoPRISMS participants and scientific results. Goal #4 was shared with the Magma and Volatiles workshop; graduate students from the Science Filmmaking program at Montana State University attended both workshops to produce outreach videos highlighting GeoPRISMS science and scientists.

Introduction:

Over the last decade, the GeoPRISMS program led to community-driven, interdisciplinary science advances in the understanding of rifts and subduction zones globally. The program was organized primarily around five primary sites between the RIE and SCD initiatives: Eastern North America (ENAM), East African Rift System (EARS), Cascadia, Alaska-Aleutians, and New Zealand. At the sunset of the GeoPRISMS program, the need for integration across primary sites in both the RIE and SCD initiatives was essential, as it was key to the original science plan, as well as highlighted by the community at the 2019 TEI Synthesis workshop. "Plate boundary deformation and geodynamics" is one of five overarching science themes that has guided the GeoPRISMS initiative over the last decade, making key contributions to these fundamental areas of research. Specifically, three science questions motivate this workshop:

1. What are the relationships between fault zone rheology and deformation and how are they constrained across a range of temporal and spatial scales in the field and lab?
2. How does the rheology of the crust and mantle influence and/or record deformation at plate boundaries?

3. What feedbacks exist between larger scale lithospheric processes, fault zone rheology, and surface processes?

Relationships between structure and deformation at plate boundaries are fundamental pieces of our understanding of the Earth's tectonic system, yet many questions remain due to the complex, interdisciplinary nature of this problem. Addressing the relationships requires a wide range of disciplines. For example, geological, geochemical, and geophysical data are needed to constrain the rheology at plate boundaries; geodetic, geomorphological, and paleoseismic data are needed to constrain current and past plate motions and crustal deformation; and experimental and modeling-based studies are needed to interpret and relate these interdisciplinary observations.

In addition, many domain-based communities within the Earth Sciences have identified topics similar to the questions highlighted here as key focus areas for addressing grand challenges within the coming decade. “How do faults slip?” and “How do plate boundary systems evolve?”, which address the relationships between structure and plate deformation on a range of temporal and spatial scales, are highlighted as future seismological grand challenges (Lay et al., 2009). Similarly, “How do fault mechanics influence earthquakes and the earthquake cycle?” and “How do solid earth's material properties vary with location over time?” are highlighted in the geodesy grand challenges report (Freytmüller et al., 2018). This GeoPRISMS synthesis workshop aimed to address the interdisciplinary needs demonstrated by these open questions, by highlighting results and discussing future directions related to GeoPRISMS research. The relationships between variation in fabric of the incoming oceanic plate with variations in plate interface structure and updated estimates of megathrust locking (Shillington et al., 2015; Li et al., 2018; Li & Freymueller, 2018) and slow slip (Todd et al., 2018; Shadlock & Schwartz, 2019) emphasize recent strides in understanding fundamental fault slip processes, while still demonstrating much future work is needed to integrate multidisciplinary observations, particularly as new techniques (e.g. offshore geodesy) are developed (Williams & Wallace, 2018). At rifted margins, results point to a potentially temporally variable and complex interplay between magmatic and fault accommodation, and their relationships with preexisting lithospheric and large-scale mantle structures (Rooney, 2017; Muirhead et al., 2018; Oliva et al., 2019; Lynner et al., 2020).

The topics addressed here also are related to burgeoning community projects, including the Subduction Zone 4D (SZ4D) initiative (McGuire et al., 2017) and the Rift-to-Ridge (R2R) initiative. These both significantly overlap with research topics on plate boundary structure and deformation in the SCD and RIE GeoPRISMS initiatives. This workshop offered a relatively unique opportunity to hear from both communities, as well as to facilitate new collaborations, particularly amongst early career scientists.

Summary:

The Structure and Deformation at Plate Boundaries GeoPRISMS Synthesis Workshop took place from March 17 - 18, 2022 at the University of Hawai'i at Mānoa in Honolulu, HI. In line with the goals of the workshop, our organizing committee was comprised of four scientists with diverse research disciplines (seismology, petrology, geochemistry, geodesy, geodynamics, experimental rock mechanics), expertise in many of the GeoPRISMS focus sites (Alaska-Aleutians, Cascadia, East African Rift System, New Zealand), and who are early-career researchers (or at least, were at the start of planning for the workshop before COVID-19 related delays). The workshop attracted a total of 64 "in-person" participants, including 23 current graduate students, with 35 distinct institutions represented. In addition, approximately 43% of all attendees identified themselves as underrepresented minorities in the Earth Sciences. Due to ongoing COVID-19 space limitations, we could not accommodate the full applicant pool for the workshop. To accommodate for this, as well as to increase access to the workshop, the keynote talks were streamed live; 33 scientists registered for this Zoom Webinar version of the workshop.

The meeting was structured around 11 keynote talks, a poster session, breakout groups, discussions related to diversity, equity, and inclusion, and FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable; Wilkenson et al., 2016), and networking opportunities for participants. The workshop began with an introduction and retrospective of the GeoPRISMS program by Demian Saffer (UTIG, UT Austin), followed by overviews of the more nascent SZ4D and R2R initiatives by Harold Tobin (University of Washington) and Jolante van Wjik (New Mexico Tech/ Los Alamos National Laboratory), respectively. There were eight additional keynote talks highlighting scientific results related to GeoPRISMS science. These covered a wide range of research disciplines (geochronology, geodesy, marine geophysics, seismology, structural geology, tectonics), and included results from each of the five primary GeoPRISMS sites. Both due to uncertainty related to the pandemic and to increase community representation, these speakers were invited based on their applications to the workshop. Seven of these eight keynotes were given by early career scientists. All participants were invited to present their research findings in a poster session, which included 50 presentations. A discussion session related to designing anti-colonial science plans and diversity, equity, and inclusion efforts was led by D. Sarah Stamps (Virginia Tech) and Cailey Condit (University of Washington). D. Sarah Stamps (Virginia Tech) also led a tutorial session related to FAIR data practices. To facilitate discussion and participation across all attendees, three breakout sessions were held where participants were randomly assigned to one of five groups. A discussion moderator and scribe was assigned for each group (total 15 moderators, and 15 scribes). Broadly, these focused on (i) identifying remaining and new science questions; (ii) data and technology needs and synergies; and (iii) visions for the future. Lastly, we hosted an interdisciplinary networking session. All participants had brief (~ 5 minute) conversations with approximately 10 other workshop attendees, and were encouraged to introduce themselves, their research interests, and discuss ideas for future plate boundary related research. Each of these sessions is discussed in more detail below.

The main workshop was preceded by a half-day early career meeting on March 16, 2022, which was open to students and untenured scientists within 10 years of their PhD. This pre-workshop meeting was attended by 48 participants (75% of attendees). This included presentations covering an overview of the GeoPRISMS program by Demian Saffer (UTIG, UT Austin), and an overview of the proposal writing process by Jenn Wade (NSF). To facilitate discussion and networking, a breakout session was organized focused on early career needs related to GeoPRISMS science. This included four breakout groups organized by career stage, two for current graduate students, one for postdocs, and one for pre-tenure faculty and researchers. Finally, a speed-mentoring session was organized to facilitate short discussions between graduate students (mentees) and postdocs or other early career scientists (mentors).

Early Career Symposium:

March 16, 2022

A half-day early career session preceding the main workshop was held on March 16. Forty seven people (approximately 2/3 of workshop participants) participated in the session. The primary objectives of the early career session were to provide opportunities to (1) learn about the GeoPRISMS program and facilitate discussion and engagement among early-career researchers in preparation for the main workshop discussion and (2) network with other early-career

researchers across disciplines. Because most of the workshop participants are at the early career stage and the GeoPRISMS program is new to some of them, the session was kicked off by introducing the GeoPRISMS program by Demian Saffer, Chair of the GeoPRISMS Office and Steering Committee. Afterward, a one-hour breakout group discussion was arranged to discuss research and career needs. The discussion topics were selected from those during the breakout sessions of the main workshop. With three primary science questions that motivated the workshop, the early-career breakout discussion focuses on the questions:

- How well can we answer these three questions at plate boundary systems?
- What do you think are the most important remaining questions with regards to understanding plate boundaries?
- What do you think are the highest priority needs for community investment to enable early career PIs in plate boundary research in the next 5 years, in terms of (1) facilities, infrastructure, and data, (2) interdisciplinary collaboration, (3) experiments, fieldwork, and modeling, and (4) Diversity, Inclusion, and Accessibility?

Four breakout groups were assigned based on career stage: two groups of graduate students, a group of postdocs, and a group of early career faculty and researchers. Although each breakout group discussion was not reported back to the entire group during the early-career session, some key takeaways are summarized below.

- Understanding the role of fluids in metasomatism and deformation and the heterogeneous properties of materials with different compositions along the plate boundary is crucial.
- More comparative studies are needed between locales and across the plate boundary type (convergent, divergent, and transform).
- Bridging processes over a wide range of time and length scales is critical and can be aided by interdisciplinary research collaboration.
- Building research and educational networks (e.g., GeoPRISMS program or CIDER workshop) is fundamental for innovative and interdisciplinary science. Better communication and education across disciplines are essential for successful interdisciplinary science; it is vital to understand not only results but also assumptions and limitations of a study outside one's field. It is time to explore building collaborative networks with data scientists and machine learning specialists.
- The community needs infrastructure that can provide dense datasets with diverse instrumentation (e.g., integrated INSAR/GNSS/seismometer/weather stations) and accessible laboratory facilities for experiments, geochronology, and observational studies with ample technical staff support.

After the breakout discussion, Jen Wade, NSF program director, explained NSF proposal processes and answered questions from participants. At the end of the early career session, a networking and mentoring event was held outside the building, keeping social-distancing. Two lines of mentees (graduate students) and mentors (postdocs and early-career scientists) were formed. A mentor-mentee pair introduced each other and their research for about 5 minutes, switching to the next person for another mentoring session.

Main Meeting:

March 17, 2022

On Day 1 we had 4 Introduction related presentations, 3 science keynote presentations, a poster session for all participants, a breakout discussion session, and moderated networking. The first introduction presentation was by Helen Janiszewski welcoming participants to the workshop, sharing norms and logistics, and introducing the major science questions this workshop aimed to address. Following this, Demian Saffer presented on the legacy of GeoPRISMS, Harold Tobin presented on the ongoing SZ4D initiatives, and Jolante van Wjik presented on the Rift-to-Ridge (R2R) initiative. The science keynote talks were from a mix of geophysical and geologic topics all related to plate boundary structure from Donna Shillington, and early career scientists Noah Phillips, and Zach Eilon. Topics included the geophysical perspective on rifting and subduction zone fault controls on deformation, the geologic record of deformation in the subduction seismogenic zone, and the complexities of extensional systems. Discussion afterwards focused

on how to integrate disparate geologic and geophysical observations of the same systems, and how different or similar the plate boundary structures of rifts and subduction zones are. Discussion continued during the lunch and poster session, where over 40 participants presented posters of their ongoing work on plate boundary structures. We then had several short pop-up presentations focused on Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (DEI) by D. Sarah Stamps and Cailey Condit focusing on how to equitably conduct research in partnership with local stakeholders in foreign countries, and how to incorporate DEI into research and reciprocal practices for interacting with Indigenous groups while doing extractive geologic work. Discussions

afterwards included sharing of resources, perspectives on equitable practices for conducting research, and ways to build graduate student-focused affinity research groups (this included the inception of the [SZ4Grads initiative](#) now operating under SZ4D).

Following this, we had our first breakout group discussion focused on identifying the remaining science questions. Questions highlighted were the role of inherited structures in both rift and subduction plate boundaries, the feedbacks amongst fluid flow, pore fluid pressure, and slip behavior, the urgent need for constitutive rheological relations for the full range of lithologies within and around these plate boundary structures, and a closer integration of geophysical observations with geologic constraints across variable temporal and spatial scales. Key takeaways from this breakout were the urgent need for interdisciplinary projects focused on the same processes from variable geophysical, geological, or experimental perspectives. Moderated networking after this discussion session included structured but informal introductions and discussion between a wide range of participants.

March 18, 2022

On Day 2 we had 5 science keynote presentations, a tutorial on FAIR data practices, and 2 breakout sessions. Keynote presentations were presented by early career scientists' Christine Chesley, Emmanuel Njinju, Wenyuan Fan, Lydia Staisch, and Théa Ragon. Topics covered slow

slip in New Zealand, mantle convection and melt generation in East Africa, low frequency earthquakes and rupture boundaries in Cascadia, as well as on and off fault deformation at both rifts and subduction zones. A FAIR data practices tutorial was delivered by D. Sarah Stamps that involved an overview of FAIR, FAIR best practices, and discussion amongst participants. Related to the FAIR data practices tutorial, we note that the data survey completed by participants documented 36 seismic and geodetic datasets with doi's spanning 7 countries and three of the GeoPRISMS focus sites (East African Rift System, Alaska-Aleutians, and New Zealand) as well as the Woodlark Rift. The two breakout groups discussed 'Data and Technology Needs and Synergies' and 'Visions for the Future'. Questions asked during the 'Data and Technology Needs and Synergies' breakout included (1) What data are needed and accessible to make connections between lab, field, and model observations at plate boundaries? (2) What observations are needed from onshore, offshore, and amphibious environments? And (3) What rapid response capabilities are needed to capture critical transient events at plate boundaries? A few key takeaways from this breakout group were that standard data formats are needed across disciplines, amphibious networks are desired that include seafloor geodesy, ocean bottom seismometers, and temperature observations, and engagement with local governments is key for rapid response capabilities. The 'Visions for the Future' breakout session focused on one question: What are the high priority needs for community investment to enable PI-driven plate boundary science in the next 5-10 years? A few key takeaways from this breakout session includes the need for long-term facilities, including permanent networks, that support data/sample storage/sharing and high performance computing resources, funding mechanisms to support interdisciplinary collaboration, and creative ways to increase diversity, inclusion, and accessibility.

Videos:

A legacy of this workshop includes the recorded keynote talks, as well as the production of a series of outreach videos interviewing scientists about their perspectives on the GeoPRISMS program. The keynote talks are archived under a YouTube Playlist available [here](#) and are available on the workshop website. The outreach videos were produced by Leif Everson and Ashley Lobao, graduate students in the Science and Natural History Filmmaking program at Montana State University. Between this and the Magma and Volatiles Workshop, eight 3-5 minute videos were produced discussing scientists' career paths, research areas, and the legacy of the GeoPRISMS program. From this workshop, the interviewed scientists were Tamara Jeppson, Kyle Murray, Samer Naif, and Lindsay Worthington. These are also available on YouTube [here](#) and on the workshop website.

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Appendices

I. Registered Participants:

Name	Institution	Email
Aarti Dwivedi	Massachusetts Institute of Technology	adwivedi@mit.edu
Alba M. Rodriguez Padilla	University of California, Davis	arodriguezpadilla@ucdavis.edu
Anne Bécel	Lamont Doherty Earth Observatory	annebcl@ldeo.columbia.edu
Asenath Kwagalakwe	Virginia Tech	asenathk@vt.edu
Bhargav Boddupalli	University of Texas at Austin	bhargav@ig.utexas.edu
Brandon Shuck	Lamont Doherty Earth Observatory	brandon.shuck@utexas.edu
Cailey Brown Condit	University of Washington	ccondit@uw.edu
Catherine Lloyd	Texas A&M University	catherine.lloyd@tamu.edu
Celine Fliedner	Rice University	cf16@rice.edu
Christine Chesley	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution	chesley@ldeo.columbia.edu
Christopher Carchedi	Lamont Doherty Earth Observatory	carchedi@ldeo.columbia.edu
Collin Brandl	University of New Mexico	cbrandl@unm.edu
Colton Lynner	University of Delaware	clynner@udel.edu
D. Sarah Stamps	Virginia Tech	dstamps@vt.edu
Daniel Doulgas	New Mexico Institute of Mining and Technology	daniel.douglas@student.nmt.edu
Demian Saffer	UTIG, UT Austin	demian@ig.utexas.edu
Donna Shillington	Northern Arizona University	donna.shillington@nau.edu
Dylan Vasey	University of California, Davis	davasey@ucdavis.edu
Eirini Poulaki	University of Texas at Austin	eirini_poulaki@utexas.edu
Elizabeth Benyshek	University of Hawai'i at Mānoa	benyshek@hawaii.edu
Emmanuel A. Njinju	Virginia Tech	njinju85@vt.edu
Eric Lindsey	University of New Mexico	eol@unm.edu
Ethan Conrad	University of Texas at Austin	econrad@utexas.edu
Fan Wang	Michigan State University	wangfa16@msu.edu
Fernando Martinez	University of Hawai'i at Mānoa	fernando@hawaii.edu
Garrett Ito	University of Hawai'i at Mānoa	gito@hawaii.edu
Greg Moore	University of Hawai'i at Mānoa	gmoore@hawaii.edu
Harold Tobin	University of Washington	htobin@uw.edu

Helen Janiszewski	University of Hawai'i at Mānoa	hajanisz@hawaii.edu
Hiroko Kitajima	Texas A&M University	kitaji@tamu.edu
James Biemiller	Scripps Institution of Oceanography, UCSD	jbiemiller@ucsd.edu
James Gaherty	Northern Arizona University	james.gaherty@nau.edu
James R Bourke	Rutgers University	jrb370@eps.rutgers.edu
Jana Schierjott	University of Hawai'i at Mānoa	jschierj@hawaii.edu
Jeff Freymueller	Michigan State University	freymuel@msu.edu
Jeff Marshall	Cal Poly Pomona	marshall@cpp.edu
Jennifer Wade	National Science Foundation	jwade@nsf.gov
Jianhua Gong	Scripps Institution of Oceanography, UCSD	j4gong@ucsd.edu
John He	University of Arizona	johnhe@email.arizona.edu
Jolante van Wijk	New Mexico Tech, Los Alamos National Laboratory	jolante.vanwijk@nmt.edu
Jonathan Weiss	NOAA/NWS Pacific Tsunami Warning Center	jonathan.weiss@noaa.gov
Kayleigh Harvey	Boston College	harveykf@bc.edu
Kennet E Flores	UNC Chapel Hill	keflores@unc.edu
Kristina Butler	University of Texas at Austin	kristina.butler@utexas.edu
Kyle Murray	University of Hawai'i at Mānoa	murray8@hawaii.edu
Lindsay Lowe Worthington	University of New Mexico	lworthington@unm.edu
Lydia Staisch	USGS	lstaisch@usgs.gov
Matt Wei	University of Rhode Island	matt-wei@uri.edu
Megan Mueller	University of Connecticut	megan.mueller@uconn.edu
Noah Phillips	Lakehead University	nphilli2@lakeheadu.ca
Paraskevi Io Ioannidi	Iowa State University	ioannidi@iastate.edu
Paul Liu	NC State University	jpliu@ncsu.edu
Ruth Aronoff	Furman University	ruth.aronoff@furman.edu
Samer Naif	Georgia Institute of Technology	snaif@eas.gatech.edu
Shi Joyce Sim	Georgia Institute of Technology	jssim@eas.gatech.edu
Tamara Aranguiz	University of Washington	tarangui@uw.edu
Tamara Jeppson	USGS	tjeppson@usgs.gov
Tanner Acquisto	Lamont Doherty Earth Observatory	acquisto@ldeo.columbia.edu
Théa Ragon	California Institute of Technology	tragon@caltech.edu

Thomas Luckie	University of Southern California	luckie@usc.edu
Valeria Cortes Rivas	Northern Arizona University	vc553@nau.edu
Wenyuan Fan	Scripps Institution of Oceanography, UCSD	wenyuanfan@ucsd.edu
William B Hawley	Lamont Doherty Earth Observatory	whawley@ldeo.columbia.edu
Yurong Zhang	Michigan State University	yurong@msu.edu
Zachary Eilon	University of California Santa Barbara	eilon@ucsb.edu
Zongshan Li	Washington University in St. Louis	zongshan.li@wustl.edu

II. Keynote Talks:

INTRODUCTION AND RELATED INITIATIVES

Demian Saffer	<i>Plate boundary deformation, structure, and mechanics: Insights from a decade of interdisciplinary research in GeoPRISMS</i>
Harold Tobin	<i>The SZ4D Initiative: Where it is Now and Where it's Headed</i>
Jolante van Wijk	<i>R2R: An update on activities from the rift, rifted margin, and seafloor spreading communities</i>

KEYNOTE SESSION I

Donna Shillington	<i>Comparing controls on rift and subduction zone faulting and deformation: examples from Alaska, Africa, Eastern North America</i>
Zachary Eilon	<i>Not so simple after all: challenging simple ideas of extensional systems</i>
Noah Phillips	<i>Plate Boundary Fault Rocks: Some observations, conundrums & potential future directions</i>

KEYNOTE SESSION II

Christine Chesley	<i>Seamounts, and slow slip, and hydrates, Oh my!--Marine electromagnetic investigations of the Hikurangi Margin, New Zealand</i>
Emmanuel A. Njinju	<i>Tomography-Based Convection and Melt Generation Beneath the Rungwe Volcanic Province, East Africa</i>
Wenyuan Fan	<i>Very low frequency earthquakes in between the seismogenic and tremor zones in Cascadia?</i>

KEYNOTE SESSION III

Lydia Staisch	<i>Synthesizing geologic and geophysical datasets along the Cascadia subduction zone to identify possible persisted earthquake rupture boundaries</i>
Théa Ragon	<i>On- and off-fault deformation: similar research directions for subduction zones and rifts systems</i>

III. Poster Presentations:

Aarti Dwivedi	<i>Evolution of slow-slip in Southern Cascadia</i>
Alba M. Rodriguez Padilla	<i>Widespread inelasticity from the 2019 Ridgecrest earthquakes: implications for the long-term evolution of fault zones</i>
Anne Bécel	<i>Along-strike variations in bending faulting and upper oceanic crustal hydration outboard of the Shumagin segment of the Alaska Peninsula subduction zone</i>
Asenath Kwagalakwe	<i>Investigating Potential Melt Sources for the Magma-Poor Albertine-Rhino Graben of the East African Rift System Using 3D Geodynamic Modeling with ASPECT</i>
Bhargav Boddupalli	<i>Rock physics modeling and inversion on sediments in the Cascadia Subduction Zone</i>
Brandon Shuck	<i>Incoming plate properties along the northern Cascadia subduction zone from new CASIE21 seismic data</i>
Cailey Condit	Brown <i>Rheology of metasedimentary rocks at the base of the subduction seismogenic zone</i>
Catherine Lloyd	<i>Drilling performance analysis of input and prism sediments at the Hikurangi Margin</i>
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Elizabeth Benyshek	<i>Tectonics of the Papua-Woodlark Region</i>
Eric Lindsey	<i>Tectonic geodesy of western Myanmar: strain partitioning and active subduction revealed by a dense new GNSS velocity field</i>
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Garrett Ito	<i>Widths of imbricate thrust blocks and the strength of the front of accretionary wedges and fold-and-thrust belts</i>
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